

LIFT

Low-Input Farming and Territories – Integrating knowledge for improving ecosystem based farming

Research and Innovation action: H2020 – 770747

Call: H2020-SFS-2016-2017

Type of action: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Work programme topic: SFS-29-2017

Duration of the project: 01 May 2018 – 30 April 2022

LIFT large-scale farmer survey questionnaire

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About the LIFT research project

Ecological approaches to farming practices are gaining interest across Europe. As this interest grows there is a pressing need to assess the potential contributions these practices may make, the contexts in which they function and their attractiveness to farmers as potential adopters. In particular, ecological agriculture must be assessed against the aim of promoting the improved performance and sustainability of farms, rural environment, rural societies and economies, together.

The overall goal of LIFT is to identify the potential benefits of the adoption of ecological farming in the European Union (EU) and to understand how socio-economic and policy factors impact the adoption, performance and sustainability of ecological farming at various scales, from the level of the single farm to that of a territory.

To meet this goal, LIFT will assess the determinants of adoption of ecological approaches, and evaluate the performance and overall sustainability of these approaches in comparison to more conventional agriculture across a range of farm systems and geographic scales. LIFT will also develop new private arrangements and policy instruments that could improve the adoption and subsequent performance and sustainability of the rural nexus. For this, LIFT will suggest an innovative framework for multi-scale sustainability assessment aimed at identifying critical paths toward the adoption of ecological approaches to enhance public goods and ecosystem services delivery. This will be achieved through the integration of transdisciplinary scientific knowledge and stakeholder expertise to co-develop innovative decision-support tools.

The project will inform and support EU priorities relating to agriculture and the environment in order to promote the performance and sustainability of the combined rural system. At least 30 case studies will be performed in order to reflect the enormous variety in the socio-economic and bio-physical conditions for agriculture across the EU.

Project consortium

No.	Participant organisation name	Country
1	INRA – Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique	FR
2	VetAgro Sup – Institut d’enseignement supérieur et de recherche en alimentation, santé animale, sciences agronomiques et de l’environnement	FR
3	SRUC – Scotland’s Rural College	UK
4	Teagasc – Agriculture and Food Development Authority	IE
5	KU Leuven – Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	BE
6	SLU – Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet	SE
7	UNIBO – Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	IT
8	BOKU – Universitaet fuer Bodenkultur Wien	AT
9	UBO – Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms – Universität Bonn	DE
10	JRC – Joint Research Centre – European Commission	BE
11	IAE-AR – Institute of Agricultural Economics	RO
12	MTA KRTK – Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Közgazdaság – és Regionális Tudományi Kutatóközpont	HU
13	IRWiR PAN – Instytut Rozwoju Wsi i Rolnictwa Polskiej Akademii Nauk	PL
14	DEMETER – Hellinikos Georgikos Organismos – DIMITRA	GR
15	UNIKENT – University of Kent	UK
16	IT – INRA Transfert S.A.	FR
17	ECOZEPT Deutschland	DE

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AES: Agri-Environment Schemes

GPS: Global Positioning System

IPM: Integrated Pest Management

IWM: Integrated Weed Management

LFA: Less Favoured Areas

PDO: Protected Designation of Origin

RTK: Real Time Kinetics

UAA: Utilised Agricultural Area

1 Summary

This questionnaire is for the survey to farmers that is to be carried out in the LIFT project, to at least 1,500 farms across the European Union (EU) in the LIFT case study areas. The LIFT large-scale farmer survey represents a key task that provides value added to the LIFT project and informs EU policy analysis as a whole. The innovation is that it collects primary qualitative and quantitative data at the farm level, but also that data will be comparable across a large geographical area, across different production sectors, as well as across different farming practices/systems. The survey aims at collecting information that is not available in existing data sources, and that will be used in the analyses of the project.

2 Introduction

This questionnaire is for the survey to farmers that is to be carried out in the LIFT project, to at least 1,500 farms across the European Union in the LIFT case study areas. The survey aims at collecting information that is not available in existing data sources, and that will be used in the analyses of the project. The questionnaire focuses on ecological practices, as defined in the LIFT sense, see Deliverable 1.1. The information gathered relates to the practices used on the farm, the drivers behind the adoption of these practices, the farm's structural and economic characteristics, the on-farm labour force, the farmer's feeling towards future agricultural policies and general characteristics of the farmer and the farm.

3 Questionnaire

Please Add
your Logo
here

Logo of Partner

LIFT

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	Data Collection Information
Q0_0	Farm ID: _____ <i>This ID is specific for this survey and is provided by the surveyor. If you do not have, leave blank.</i>
Q0_1	Who is collecting the data for this survey? (multiple selections allowed) <input type="checkbox"/> The farmer him/herself <input type="checkbox"/> Surveyor from research staff <input type="checkbox"/> Student surveyor <input type="checkbox"/> Surveyor from survey company
Q0_2	How is the data collected? (multiple selections allowed) <input type="checkbox"/> Interview face-to-face <input type="checkbox"/> Phone interview <input type="checkbox"/> Pen and paper <input type="checkbox"/> Internet
Q0_3	When is the data collected? (DD/MM/YYYY) _____

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Introductory note

In a changing policy environment, farmers are increasingly being rewarded for farming in a way that provides public goods. Public goods provide environmental benefits such as improved soil or water quality, conserving biodiversity, or reducing greenhouse gas emissions. They also include social benefits such as animal health and welfare, promoting social capital in rural communities, or maintaining the rural landscape and heritage.

Some farming practices have been linked to the generation of public goods more than others such as practices that minimise the use of inputs, for example, pesticides or chemical fertilisers, or that promote biodiversity. These practices are common in organic or agro-ecological farming systems, but also in more conventional farming systems, and include the use of precision technologies or integrated pest management.

We will refer to these practices as **ecological farming practices** throughout this survey.

We are interested in finding out how widespread these practices are across **[Name of the country]**, what factors influence their adoption, and what might encourage their adoption in the future.

The information you provide will enable a better understanding of the benefits and challenges to adopting more ecological practices and what support mechanisms might be required to further enable their uptake.

Please note the information you supply is entirely confidential, your identity remains anonymous, and the data obtained is downloaded onto a secure server and not distributed to third parties.

[Add thanks and link to GDPR information sheet]

- ❖ The survey should be answered by the **decision maker of the farm**, or any of the decision makers of the farm if there are several.
- ❖ The questions relate to **the year 2018**. It may be the calendar year (January to December), the seasonal year or the tax year: it is up to you to decide which year is best suited for your case, but the year should be 12 months long.

Section 1

General characteristics of the farmer and the farm

Farm characteristics

Q 1	Where is most of the farm located?	
Q1_1	Country	
Q1_2	NUTS3 code or the name of the administrative region	
<i>Notes</i>	<i>To be filled in by surveyor or list of options</i>	

Q 2	Is part or all of your farm located in:	
Q2_1	Less favoured areas (LFA)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q2_2	Natura 2000 area (FADN Code: 190)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q2_3	Water Directive (2000/60/EC) area (FADN Code: 200)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>Notes</i>	<i>Could be filled in by surveyor on the basis of secondary data.</i>	

Q 3	Indicate the altitude of most of your farm:	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Most of the farmland below 300 m <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the farmland at 300 m to 600 m <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the farmland at 600 m or over	
<i>Notes</i>	<i>Could be filled in by surveyor on the basis of secondary data.</i>	

Q 4	Indicate average annual precipitation on your farm from 2016 to 2018:	
	<input type="checkbox"/> < 200 mm <input type="checkbox"/> 200 – 399 mm <input type="checkbox"/> 400 – 599 mm <input type="checkbox"/> 600 – 799 mm <input type="checkbox"/> 800 - 1000 mm <input type="checkbox"/> > 1000 mm	
<i>Notes</i>	<i>Could be filled in by surveyor on the basis of secondary data.</i>	

Q 5	Would you say the average soil quality on your farm is:	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Very good <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Very poor	
<i>Notes</i>	<i>Could be filled in by surveyor on the basis of secondary data. If the information is not available beforehand to the surveyor, this is the own perception of the farmer of his/her farm. There may be diverse soil quality on the farm, and we are looking for an average for the whole farm.</i>	

Q 6	In 2018, what was the management structure of the farm?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Individual (family) farm / sole holder <input type="checkbox"/> Partnership (several business partners manage the farm) <input type="checkbox"/> Company (not partnership) with profit objective <input type="checkbox"/> Company (not partnership) with non-profit objective <input type="checkbox"/> Other; please specify: / _____ /

Q 7_1	Indicate the main production type of your farm in 2018
	<input type="checkbox"/> Specialist cereal, oilseed and protein crops <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist other fieldcrops (dry pulses, potatoes, sugar beet, fibre crops, hop, tobacco, cotton, sugar can, other industrial crops, root crops, field vegetables) <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist horticulture <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist wine <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist orchards (excluding olives) <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist olives <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist dairy milk <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist cattle <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist sheep and goats <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist poultry <input type="checkbox"/> Specialist pigs <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed crops <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed livestock <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed crops and livestock <input type="checkbox"/> Other
Q7_2	Did your farm have livestock in 2018?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q7_2a	If no, do you plan to introduce any livestock in the next 5 years?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Notes	<i>Q7_1 and Q7_2 could be filled in by surveyor on the basis of secondary data. If the information is not available beforehand to the surveyor, this is the own perception of the farmer based on the main source of revenue from production.</i>

Q 8	Have you participated in agri-environment schemes (AES)?			
		[A] Participating in 2018	[B] Previously participated	[C] Never Participated
Q8_1	Organic AES	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q8_2	Other AES	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	<i>Examples of national AES to be provided by surveyor.</i>			

Q 9		Have you participated in any of the following certification schemes?		
		[A] Participating in 2018	[B] Previously participated	[C] Never participated
Q9_1	European Protected Designation of Origin (PDO)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q9_2	European organic certification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q9_3	Other eco labels/standards Specify the scheme: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	<i>Examples of national eco labels/standards to be provided by surveyor.</i>			

Q 10		What was your total farm turnover * in 2018?	
Q10_1	_____	Specify the currency:	
		To whom in the supply chain did you sell your products in 2018? Please estimate the percentage of your turnover * via each channel in 2018.	
Q10_2a	Retailer *	_____	%
Q10_2b	Processor	_____	%
Q10_2c	Wholesaler/Merchant *	_____	%
Q10_2d	Direct to consumer	_____	%
Q10_2e	Producer organisations/Agricultural cooperatives/Other collectors	_____	%
Q10_2f	Other	_____	%
Notes	<p><i>*Turnover represents farm's income from net sales plus payments/subsidies before costs/taxes.</i></p> <p><i>*Retailers sell directly to end consumers.</i></p> <p><i>*Wholesalers or merchants do not sell directly to end consumers. They are the equivalent position in the supply chain of cooperatives but with a different structure.</i></p>		

Q 11		Please indicate your land use for the year 2018	
Q11	TOTAL Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) (all agricultural area, including arable, grassland, vegetables, orchards etc.) Including (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) below		Ha
Q11_0	Do you intend to increase your UAA in the next 5 years?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Please specify below the various parts of your area in 2018:			
Q11_1	(1) Total arable area (this includes area for arable crops, permanent and temporary grassland, and vegetables and fruits that are not part of perennial crop area, e.g. strawberries)		Ha
Q11_1a	➔ Thereof arable land for temporary grassland-type forage production (such as clover grass, alfalfa, feeding rye, other grass, where arable land is only ploughed every couple of years)		Ha
Please specify the use of this temporary grassland:			
Q11_1ai	Type of use (if both apply, select both): <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Grazing		
Q11_1aii	Intensity*: <input type="checkbox"/> up to 2 uses/year <input type="checkbox"/> more than 2 uses/year		
Q11_2	(2) Total permanent grassland area * (on permanent grassland no ploughing takes place ever)		Ha
Thereof...			
Q11_2a	➔ (a) permanent grassland area with pure meadows * (only cut) thereof...		Ha
Q11_2ai	➔ (i) area with meadows with up to 2 cuts per year		Ha
Q11_2b	➔ (b) permanent grassland area with pure pastures * (only grazed) thereof...		Ha
Q11_2bi	➔ (i) area with continuous grazing/pasture *		Ha
Q11_2bii	➔ (ii) area with strip grazing pasture *		Ha
Q11_2biii	➔ (iii) area with paddock grazing *		Ha
Q11_2c	➔ (c) permanent grassland area with mixed use (grazed and cut) thereof...		Ha
Q11_2ci	➔ (i) area with meadows/pastures with up to 2 uses per year		Ha
Q11_3	(3) Total perennial crops area :		Ha
Thereof...			
Q11_3a	➔ (a) area with orchards, excluding olives (e.g. apples, oranges, perennial berries)		Ha
Q11_3ai	Year of plantation of major part of orchards (YYYY)		
Q11_3aai	Density: average number of trees per Ha		
Q11_3b	➔ (b) area with olive groves		Ha
Q11_3bi	Year of plantation of major part of olive groves (YYYY)		
Q11_3bii	Density: average number of trees per Ha		
Q11_3c	➔ (c) area with vineyards		Ha
Q11_3ci	Year of plantation of major part of vineyards (YYYY)		Ha
Q11_3cii	Density: average number of vinestock per Ha		
(4) Fallow area :			
Q11_4a	UAA left fallow permanently		Ha
Q11_4b	UAA left fallow in 2018 (i.e. not including UAA left fallow permanently)		Ha

Q11_5	(5) Forest/Wooded area on UAA (e.g. tree nursery, energy wood, coppices etc)	Ha
Q11_6	Forest/wooded area not in UAA (not part of UAA, not part of arable land nor of grassland)	Ha
Notes	<p>* When indicating the intensity of the arable land for temporary grassland-type forage production, please ADD uses for cutting AND uses for grazing (e.g. 1 cutting and 2 grazing: tick “more than 2 uses/year”).</p> <p>Permanent grassland: land used permanently (for several - usually more than five - consecutive years) to grow herbaceous forage crops, through cultivation (sown) or naturally (self-seeded); not included in the crop rotation scheme.</p> <p>Pure meadow: grassland that has been harvested predominantly by mowing over the last 5 years or since the establishment of the sward if it is less than 5 years old.</p> <p>Pure pasture: grassland that has been harvested predominantly by grazing over the last 5 years or since the establishment of the sward if it is less than 5 years old.</p> <p>Continuous grazing/pasture: Continuous grazing is a one-pasture system in which livestock have unrestricted access to the pasture area throughout the grazing season. It is a simple system to implement and manage, with minimal capital investment and movement of animals.</p> <p>Strip grazing pasture: Strip grazing is a grazing management system that involves giving livestock a fresh allocation of pasture each day. It is usually organised within a paddock grazing system and the animals are controlled by the use of an electric fence.</p> <p>Paddock grazing/Intensive rotational grazing: Intensive rotational grazing is a system with many pastures, oftentimes called paddocks or cells. Livestock are moved from paddock to paddock based on forage growth and utilisation. The number of paddocks and frequency of rotation depend upon many factors, including the type (e.g. cattle, sheep) and class (e.g. dairy cows, heifers, bulls) of livestock and production goals of the manager.</p>	

Q 12	Please specify the amount of utilised agricultural area (UAA) in 2018 that you:	
Q12_1	Owned	_____Ha
Q12_2	Rented in	_____Ha
Q12_3	Rented out	_____Ha

Q 13	Do you plan to continue farming on the farm in the next five years?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I plan to continue farming on the farm for the next five years <input type="checkbox"/> No, the farm will be continued by family member(s) <input type="checkbox"/> No, the farm will be continued outside the family <input type="checkbox"/> Too early to say

Q 14 Composition of total net household income * in 2018			
[A] Please tick the types of income which was relevant for your household in 2018. Please think of all persons contributing to your household income (e.g. partner, children, etc.) Multiple selections allowed.		[B] Please estimate, how much did this component contributed to the total net household income (sum =100%)	
Q14_1	Net household income from farming (without forestry, agri-tourism and contract work which are listed in Q14_2 to Q14_4) <i>(includes all income from on-farm agricultural crop and animal production (e.g. direct sales of products), and all farming-related subsidies (e.g. CAP Pillar 1, CAP Pillar 2, Natura 2000, non EU subsidies, etc.)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Q14_2	Net household income from forestry <i>(includes all income from own forestry, and the forestry-related subsidies)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Q14_3	Net household income from agri-tourism/gastronomy <i>(includes all income from e.g. renting out rooms to tourists, gastronomy, etc.)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Q14_4	Net household income from agricultural/forestry contract work for others <i>(includes e.g. paid agricultural/forestry/municipality work via machinery ring, etc.)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Q14_5	Net household income from off-farm employment <i>(includes all income from paid non-agricultural work e.g. for a company, institution, etc.)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Q14_6	Other source of net household income <i>(e.g. health care, child education, arts and crafts, land/building/machinery rentals, financial earnings, etc.)</i> (specify: / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____ %
Notes	<p>* Total household income is a measure of the combined incomes of all people belonging to the household**. It includes every form of income, e.g. farm income, salaries and wages from off-farm employment, retirement income, investment gains, etc.</p> <p>* Total NET household income is total household income, after taxes and mandatory contributions (e.g. social-security) have been deducted.</p> <p>** A household consists of one or more people who live in the same home and share meals.</p>		

Human capital of the farm

Q 15	Besides you, how many family members (paid and unpaid) 16 years or older, worked on the farm in 2018?

<i>Notes</i>	<i>If none (that is to say if you were the only one working), then indicate 0.</i>

Family human capital (paid and unpaid)												
<i>To be filled only for those family members 16 years or older working on the farm</i>	Q15_1	Q15_2	Q15_3	Q15_4	Q15_5	Q15_6	Q15_7	Q15_8	Q15_9	If yes:		
	Gender * See codes below	Education * See codes below	Age (Years)	Number of years of agricultural experience	Is this person a decision maker on the farm?	When did you start as a decision maker on this farm? (YYYY)	Number of hours per week (including week-ends) working on farm on average in 2018	Number of weeks (including week-ends) vacation in 2018	Was the person paid in 2018?	Q15_10	Q15_11	Q15_txt
										Average gross wage (before tax) per week or per month in 2018	Specify if per week or per month	Specify currency
[A] You	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No				<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month	
[B] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No				<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month	

LIFT large-scale farmer survey

[C] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[D] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[E] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[F] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[G] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[H] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[I] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month
[J] Family member	<input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> NR	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 7			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sole <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, joint <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month

Notes

* **Gender:** *F: Female, M: Male, NR: Don't prefer to say*

* **Education codes:** *1: No schooling, 2: Primary school, 3: Middle or secondary school, 4: High school or sixth form college – agricultural, 5: High school or sixth form college – non-agricultural, 6: University – agricultural, 7: University – non-agricultural*

Q 16 Number of non-family hired workers (including seasonal workers) on the farm in 2018: _____

If the answer to Q16 is 0, go directly to **Q19.**

Q 17 Farm employment for non-family hired workers (including seasonal workers)								
Q17_1	Q17_2	Q17_3	Q17_4	Q17_5	Q17_6	Q17_7	Q17_txt	Q17_8
Share of non-family workers per gender	Share of non-family workers per education	Number of years of agricultural experience: average over all non-family workers	Average number of hours per week (including week-ends) working on farm in 2018: average over all non-family workers	Number of weeks (including week-ends) vacation in 2018: average over all non-family workers	Average gross wage (before tax) per week or per month in 2018: average over all non-family workers	Specify if per week or per month	Specify currency	Share of non-family workers who travelled from another country
_____ % Female _____ % Male _____ % Don't prefer to say	_____ % No schooling _____ % Primary school _____ % Middle or secondary school _____ % High school or sixth form college-agricultural _____ % High school or sixth form college-non-agricultural _____ % University – agricultural _____ % University – non-agricultural					<input type="checkbox"/> Per week <input type="checkbox"/> Per month		_____ %

Q 18	Out of the non-family hired workers, did you employ seasonal workers in 2018?	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
	If yes:	
Q18_1	In 2018, how many?	_____ number of seasonal workers
Q18_2	In 2018, how long for?	_____ average number of weeks worked per seasonal worker

Q 19	If it were possible, how would you improve the working conditions on the farm?					
		Strongly disagree 1	Somewhat disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Somewhat agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q19_1	Reduce the workload generally	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q19_2	Reduce the intensity of work at certain times of the year	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q19_3	Reduce the level of physical work	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q19_4	Reduce the amount of mental workload	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q19_5	Reduce the isolation from working on the farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section 2

Current and future production practices

Please answer **all questions** with color coded blue. That is to say:

- Q20 to Q25
- Q28
- Q29
- Q38 to Q43

If your farm grew **CROPS** (temporary and permanent grassland excluded) in 2018, please also answer questions colour coded yellow.

That is to say:

- Q26
- Q27

If your farm had **GRASSLAND** (temporary or permanent) in 2018, please also answer questions colour coded green.

That is to say:

- Q30

If your farm had **LIVESTOCK** in 2018, please also answer questions colour coded red.

That is to say:

- Q31 to Q37

Pest and plant disease management

Q 20	[A] In 2018 did you use the following pest control products to manage pests and plant diseases?		[B] When did you start using these products?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply these products in 2018?	[D] Quantity applied in 2018: on average, was it lower than recommended by manufacturer?	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes may relate to the UAA across which the practice is applied or the quantity applied)
	<p>If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>		1– Less than 5 years ago 2– 5-10 years ago 3– More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%		1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q20_1	Chemical products (insecticides/fungicides)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q20_2	Chemical products allowed by organic regulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q 21	[A] In 2018 did you use any alternative methods to control pests and plant diseases e.g. biological controls or variety selection?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] What was the origin of input that you used in 2018?	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes may relate to the UAA across which the practice is applied or the quantity applied)
	If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5 -10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-From within the farm 2- From neighbouring farms 3- Elsewhere (Multiple allowed)	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q21_1	Biological controls* <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q21_2	Pest/disease resistant/tolerant varieties <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q21_3	Other (specify: / _____ /) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	* Examples of biological controls include: beneficial predators / parasitoids, pathogens** (bacteria, fungi, viruses), sexual confusion / use of pheromones, use of trap plants. ** Examples of pathogens include: <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> , <i>Ampelomyces quisqualis</i> , <i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i> , <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> , <i>Bacillus firmus</i> , <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Bacillus pumilis</i> , <i>Coniothyrium minitans</i> , <i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i> , <i>Pythium oligandrum</i> , <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> , <i>Streptomyces griseoviridis</i> , <i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> , <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> . Examples of commercial names: AQ 10 WG, Botector, Amylo-X, Flocter, Serenade Max, Serenade Natria, Contans WG, Bioact WG, Polyversum, MicoSTOP, Patriot Dry, Remedier, Rootshield, Trium G.				

Q 22	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following to inform your decision making on pest management?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the UAA to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5 -10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q22_1	Integrated pest management principles (IPM)* <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q22_2	Precision technologies* <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	* IPM principles may include use of models to predict pest outbreaks, on field monitoring to detect pest presence and abundance, models to help decide when to apply insecticides e.g. above a certain level of infestation. * Precision technologies include e.g. GPS technologies to map pest infestations and guide spray, Real Time Kinetics (RTK), laser technology, computer guided spray nozzles to precisely target spray and reduce overspray.			

Weed management

Q 23	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following weed control products to manage weeds?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] Quantity applied in 2018: on average, was it lower than recommended by manufacturer?	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes may relate to the UAA across which the practice is applied or the quantity applied)
	<p>If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%		1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q23_1	Chemical products (herbicides) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q23_2	Products allowed by organic regulations <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q 24	[A] In 2018 did you use any additional practices to manage weeds?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] What was the origin of input that you used in 2018?	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes may relate to the UAA across which the practice is applied or the quantity applied)
	If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-From within the farm 2- From neighbouring farms 3- Elsewhere (Multiple allowed)	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q24_1	Mulching * with organic/biodegradable material <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_2	Mulching * with an inorganic material <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_3	Machine weeding <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_4	Manual weeding <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_5	Thermal weed control <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_6	Varieties tolerant * of weeds <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q24_7	Other (please specify / _____ /) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* Mulching: a protective covering, usually (but not necessarily) of organic matter such as leaves, straw, or peat, placed around plants to prevent the evaporation of moisture, the freezing of roots, and the growth of weeds. Inorganic mulching includes plastic films, gravel, pebbles, crushed stones.</p> <p>* Tolerance implies ability to outcompete or varieties that grow on a different cycle to minimise competition.</p>				

Q 25	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following to inform your decision making on weed management?		[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the UAA to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4		1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q25_1	Integrated weed management (IWM) * principles	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q25_2	Precision technologies * to guide herbicide application	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* IWM principles may include use of models to predict composition of weeds, on field monitoring of weed composition, models to help decide when to apply herbicide e.g. above a certain level of infestation.</p> <p>* Precision technologies include e.g. GPS technologies to map pest infestations and guide spray, Real Time Kinetics (RTK), laser technology, computer guided spray nozzles to precisely target spray and reduce overspray.</p>				

Fertilisation and soil management of crop area

Q 26	[A] In 2018 did you use the following fertilisation and soil management practices on your crop area? <i>Crop area includes area with arable crops and area with perennial crops (excluding temporary and permanent grassland)</i>	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your crop area did you apply this practice in 2018? Note: for Q26_10 (leaving crop residues on soil), indicate % of arable crop area covered in winter.	[D] What was the origin of input that you used in 2018?	[E] Quantity applied in 2018	[F] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes may relate to the crop area to which the practice is applied or the quantity applied where applicable)
	If No ► go to column [F] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-From within the farm 2- From neighbouring farms 3- Elsewhere (Multiple allowed)	Aggregate quantity of nitrogen in kg of nitrogen (N) per ha of crop area	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q26_1	Conventional tillage * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_2	Conservation tillage * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_3	No tillage * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_4	Application of inorganic fertilisers <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_5	Application of animal manure <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_6	Application of sewage sludge and other sludge * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_7	Application of compost * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

						<input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150	
Q26_8	Application of soil amendments*	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_9	Green manuring *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_10	Leaving crop residues on soil (Note: in column [C], indicate % of arable crop area covered in winter)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_11	Planting of N fixing crops (specify which crops: /_____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_12	Planting of catch crops * (specify which crops: /_____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_13	Planting of cover crops * (specify which crops /_____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q26_14	Other (specify /_____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Notes	<p>* Conventional tillage: applying power to break up and rearrange the entire topsoil structure.</p> <p>* Conservation tillage: a practice used in conventional agriculture to reduce the effects of tillage on soil erosion. However, it still depends on tillage as the structure forming element in the soil.</p> <p>* No tillage/zero tillage: the simple technique of drilling seed into the soil with little or no prior land preparation.</p> <p>* Sludge is muddy or slushy material produced by processing wastewater (sewage sludge) or pit latrine/septic tanks (fecal sludge).</p> <p>* Compost: a mixture of decaying organic matter, as from leaves and manure, used to improve soil structure and provide nutrients. Breaking down organic waste into humus that is reused as a beneficial nutrient can be done in several ways: vermicomposting, which is most beneficial for composting food waste; aerobic composting (with air); and anaerobic composting (without air).</p> <p>* Soil amendments: materials designed to promote plant health and soil structure, to provide a better environment for roots. They provide a foundation for success while improving the physical and chemical properties of soil, such as water infiltration and retention, drainage, aeration, and structure.</p> <p>* Green manuring: refers to a cover crop grown to help maintain soil organic matter and increase nitrogen availability that is subsequently incorporated into the soil. In green manuring, crop residues (from cover crops, N fixing crops etc.) are buried into the soil. Legumes are often used because they have rhizobia bacteria living in their root nodules that are able to fix nitrogen from the air and add it to the soil. Green manure is incorporated into the soil for the purpose of soil improvement. May include spontaneous crops, plants or weeds.</p>						

* **Catch crop:** a rapidly growing plant that can be intercropped between rows of the main crop; often used as a green manure.
 * **Cover crop:** a crop grown to prevent soil erosion by covering the soil with living vegetation and roots that hold on to the soil. Cover crops are also grown to help maintain soil organic matter and increase nitrogen availability (green manure crop), and to “hold on” to excess nutrients (a catch crop) still in the soil, following an economic crop. Other benefits of cover crops include weed suppression and attraction of beneficial insects.

Q 27	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following to inform your decision making on fertiliser application and soil management on farm?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the UAA to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q27_1	Precision technologies * to target application rate (variable rate application) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q27_2	Machine controlled application * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q27_3	Soil mapping <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* Precision technologies include e.g. GPS technologies to map pest infestations and guide spray, Real Time Kinetics (RTK), laser technology, computer guided spray nozzles to precisely target spray and reduce overspray. * Machine controlled application means that there is a tool or a device that adjusts the spreading/spraying rate based on e.g. sensors that assess Nitrogen needs and uptake of crops. Such devices are mounted on tractors and connected to the spreader or sprayer: here is an example of existing commercial available products: https://www.yara.co.uk/crop-nutrition/tools-and-services/n-sensor/</p>			

Seeds

Q 28	In 2018 where did you get your seeds, cuttings or plantlets, from? (Multiple selections allowed)	<input type="checkbox"/> Own production <input type="checkbox"/> Other farmers / community seed banks * <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial providers
Notes	<p>* Community seed bank: a community seed system is based on seed saving and aims to conserve existing varieties and make them available to the local community. Traditional seed storage and exchange mechanisms and can take several forms: community seed exchange; organised seed banks; seed saver's networks.</p>	

Crop diversification and crop rotation

Q 29	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following practices?		[B] When did you start using this system of practice?	[C] What was the number of crops in 2018	[D] Typical rotation period and typical fallow period	[E] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?	[F] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the UAA to which the practice is applied or to the number of crops used)
	<p>If No ► go to column [F] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>		1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	Number of crops ...	Typical duration	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q29_1	Crop rotation *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	... in a typical rotation: ____	____ years a field is typically planted again with the same crop	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q29_2	Crop diversification *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	... grown on the farm: ____		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q29_3	Selection of traditional/locally adapted varieties	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	... from such varieties: ____		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q29_4	Mixed cropping * (including intercropping *, alley cropping, relay cropping *; does NOT INCLUDE agroforestry)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	... grown on the same field at the same time: ____		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q29_5	Do you allow fields to lay fallow in general?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		____ months the field is left fallow on average	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* Crop rotation: Crop rotation on arable land is the practice of alternating annual crops grown on a specific field in a planned pattern or sequence in successive crop years so that crops of the same species are not grown without interruption on the same field.</p> <p>* Crop diversification: number of crops grown within the same growing season.</p> <p>* Mixed cropping: a system of sowing two or three crops together on the same land, one being the main crop and the others the subsidiaries.</p> <p>* Intercropping: growing two or more crops as a mixture in the same field at the same time. Intercropping can be one way of adding diversity to a crop system. It is a form of mixed cropping.</p> <p>* Alley cropping: growing crops between rows of trees.</p> <p>* Relay cropping: a form of mixed cropping in which the second crop is started amidst the first crop before it has been harvested.</p>						

Grassland management

Q 30	[A] In 2018 did you use the following fertilisation and soil management practices on your grassland? <i>Note: This question applies to both temporary and permanent grassland (pastures and meadows).</i>	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your grassland area did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] What was the origin of input that you used in 2018?	[E] Quantity applied in 2018	[F] Typical frequency	[G] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the pasture area)
	If No ► go to column [G] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-From within the farm 2- From neighbouring farms 3- Elsewhere (Multiple allowed)	Aggregate quantity of nitrogen in kg of nitrogen (N) per ha of grassland area	Frequency mowing / frequency reseeding	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q30_1	Application of inorganic fertilisers <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_2	Application of animal manure <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_3	Application of sewage sludge or other sludge * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_4	Application of compost * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_5	Application of soil amendments * <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

						<input type="checkbox"/> > 150 <input type="checkbox"/> 0-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-100 <input type="checkbox"/> 100-150 <input type="checkbox"/> > 150		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_6	Other (specify: / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_7	Mowing	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			Number of mows per year: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q30_8	Reseeding	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			One reseeded each _____ years	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* Sludge is muddy or slushy material produced by processing wastewater (sewage sludge) or pit latrine/septic tanks (fecal sludge).</p> <p>* Compost: a mixture of decaying organic matter, as from leaves and manure, used to improve soil structure and provide nutrients. Breaking down organic waste into humus that is reused as a beneficial nutrient can be done in several ways: vermicomposting, which is most beneficial for composting food waste; aerobic composting (with air); and anaerobic composting (without air).</p> <p>* Soil amendments: materials designed to promote plant health and soil structure, to provide a better environment for roots. They provide a foundation for success while improving the physical and chemical properties of soil, such as water infiltration and retention, drainage, aeration, and structure.</p>							

Livestock

Q 31	[A] How many of the following livestock did you have in 2018?		[B] Since when has this been on average the number of livestock heads on your farm?	[C] How many months or days of the year did they spend outdoors in 2018?		[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the number of livestock heads?	[E] How many of livestock traditional breeds typical of your area and local breeds in danger of being lost to farming did you have in 2018?		[F] In the next five years do you plan to change the number of animals of traditional breeds and/or of breeds in danger?
	<p>If zero ▶ go to columns [D] and [F] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>	Number of livestock heads in 2018 (indicate 0 if none)	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	Number of months or days in the year	Specify if months or days	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase	[E_a] Number of livestock heads from traditional breeds typical of your area (indicate 0 if none)	[E_b] Number of livestock units heads from local breeds in danger of being lost to farming (indicate 0 if none)	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q31_1	Dairy cows		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_2	Cull dairy cows		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_3	Calves for fattening		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_4	Suckler cows		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_5	Other cattle		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_6	Goats (breeding females)		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_7	Other goats		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_8	Ewes		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3		<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q31_9	Other sheep	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_10	Breeding sows	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_11	Other pigs	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_12	Laying hens	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_13	Other chicken	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_14	Other poultry	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q31_15	Other animals	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> months <input type="checkbox"/> days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	According to Regulation 807/2014 art. 7 par 3. The list of breeds in danger is established by national/regional Rural Development Programs.				

Q 32	In 2018 did some or all of your livestock share any forage area?
Q32	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q32_1	If yes, number of hectares shared: _____
Notes	A share forage area is a private pasture area which is used by more than one farmer.

Q 33	In 2018 did some or all of your livestock graze on common land?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Livestock feed

Q 34	[A] Did you use these types of feed in 2018? <i>Answer for each type of livestock on your farm and each type of feed in 2018</i>		[B] Duration that feedtype was given in 2018	[C] When did you start feeding your livestock this way?	[D] From where did you source the materials for this practice in 2018?	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change the duration each feed is given?
	<p style="background-color: #00FFFF; padding: 2px;">If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>		Number of months in 2018	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1-From within the farm 2-From neighbouring farms 3-Elsewhere <i>If more than one option applies, please specify the % for each option (e.g. hay might be in part produced in farm and in part purchased outside)</i>	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Feed for dairy cows						
Q34_1a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_1h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for cull dairy cows						
Q34_2a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_2h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Feed for calves for fattening							
Q34_3a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_3h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Feed for suckler cows							
Q34_4a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_4h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Feed for other cattle							
Q34_5a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_5h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Feed for goats (breeding females)							
Q34_6a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_6b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_6c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	

LIFT large-scale farmer survey

Q34_6d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_6e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_6f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_6g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_6h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for other goats						
Q34_7a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_7h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for ewes						
Q34_8a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_8h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for other sheep						
Q34_9a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_9g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q34_9h	Other:_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for breeding sows						
Q34_10a	Concentrated feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10b	Feed grain (wheat, barley, oats, triticale)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10c	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10d	Soy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10e	Feed beans/peas	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10f	Potato protein	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10g	Grassfeed (like pellets or such)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10h	Grazing (pasture, forest, crop residues)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_10i	Other:_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for other pigs						
Q34_11a	Concentrated feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11b	Feed grain (wheat, barley, oats, triticale)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11c	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11d	Soy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11e	Corn-cob-mix	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11f	Feed beans/peas	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11g	Potato protein	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11h	Supplement feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11i	Grassfeed (like alfalfa, clover or other grass-pellets)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11j	Grazing (pasture, forest, crop residues)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11k	Whey	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_11l	Other:_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for laying hens						
Q34_12a	Feed grain (wheat, corn, oats, barley, triticale)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q34_12b	Feeding lime	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12c	Concentrated feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12d	Supplement feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12e	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12f	Grassfeed (like alfalfa, clover or other grass-pellets)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12g	Soy (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12h	Linseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12i	Rapeseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12j	Protein feed (e.g. peas, beans)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12k	Oil	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12l	Potato protein	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12m	'Grazing' on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12n	'Grazing' on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_12o	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Feed for other chicken					
Q34_13a	Feed grain (wheat, corn, oats, barley, triticale)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13b	Concentrated feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13c	Supplement feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13d	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13e	Grassfeed (like alfalfa, clover or other grass-pellets)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13f	Soy (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13g	Linseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13h	Rapeseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13i	Protein feed (e.g. peas, beans)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13j	Oil	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13k	Potato protein	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13l	'Grazing' on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13m	'Grazing' on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q34_13n	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Feed for other poultry							
Q34_14a	Feed grain (wheat, corn, oats, barley, triticale)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14b	Feeding lime	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14c	Concentrated feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14d	Supplement feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14e	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14f	Grassfeed (like alfalfa, clover or other grass-pellets)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14g	Soy (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14h	Linseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14i	Rapeseed (expeller/cake)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14j	Protein feed (e.g. peas, beans)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14k	Oil	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14l	Potato protein	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14m	'Grazing' on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14n	'Grazing' on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_14o	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Feed for other animals							
Q34_15a	Grazing on pasture	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15b	Conserved forage: silage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15c	Conserved forage: hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15d	Concentrates	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15e	Grains	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15f	Beets	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15g	Grazing on crop residues	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Q34_15h	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 2: ___% <input type="checkbox"/> 3: ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	

Livestock disease management

Q 35	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following practices of livestock disease management?	[B] When did you start this practice?	[C] In the next five years do you plan to change this practice? (changes relate to the number of animals to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [C] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q35_1	Use of antibiotics for prevention, or for treatment and prevention	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q35_2	Use of antibiotics only for treatment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q35_3	Alternative remedies (e.g. homeopathy or essential oils)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q35_4	Physical measures (e.g. separation, aeration, minimum days outdoors)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q35_5	Trait selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q35_6	Other (please specify / _____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Livestock location

Q 36	[A] In 2018 did you change the location of your livestock through the year?	[B] When did you start this pattern of movement this way?	[C] What duration in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the pattern of movement? (changes relate to the number of animals to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	Average number of grazing days per animal for each practice in 2018	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q36_1	Local rotation around farm *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	___ number of grazing days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q36_2	Seasonal movement (stay in summer rangelands, spend grazing on mountainous rangelands)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	___ number of grazing days	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	* Local rotation refers to moving livestock to different grazing areas of the farm			

Manure and slurry management

Q 37	[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following manure and slurry management practices?		[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] In the next five years do you plan to change this practice? (changes relate to the size of equipment used or the number of animals concerned by the practice)
	If No ► go to column [C] where you should select between options 3 and 4		1– Less than 5 years ago 2– 5-10 years ago 3– More than 10 years ago	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q37_1	Specific bedding type for animals (e.g. straw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q37_2	Specific storage facility to reduce GHG emissions (e.g. covered pit)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q37_3	Specific storage facility to reduce leakage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q37_4	Digester	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q37_5	Composting *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q37_6	Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	* Compost: a mixture of decaying organic matter, as from leaves and manure, used to improve soil structure and provide nutrients. Breaking down organic waste into humus that is reused as a beneficial nutrient can be done in several ways: vermicomposting, which is most beneficial for composting food waste; aerobic composting (with air); and anaerobic composting (without air).			

Landscape features and habitats

Q 38	[A] In 2018 was there any of the following features on your UAA?		[B] When did you start maintaining / creating these features?	[C] What % of your UAA was covered by these features in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the features listed? (changes relate to the management of the UAA covered by the features)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4		1– Less than 5 years ago 2– 5-10 years ago 3– More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 10% 3- >10% ≤ 15% 4- >15% ≤ 20% 5- >20%	1-Remove features 2-Stop managing features 3-No change 4-Introduce new features 5-Increase features
Q38_1	Hedgerows	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_2	Bushes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_3	Wet areas	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_4	Tree lines	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_5	Woodland on UAA (coppice, afforrested areas, woodlots, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_6	Isolated trees	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_7	Field margins *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_8	Buffer strips *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_9	Flower strips *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_10	Terraces	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q38_11	Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Notes	<p>* Field margins: herbaceous cover adjacent to cropland with a width between 1 and 20 metres, on which there shall be no agricultural production.</p> <p>* Buffer strips: herbaceous cover adjacent to cropland minimum width 1 meter (but single member states can increase it). They shall be located on or adjacent to a field in such a way that their long edges are parallel to the edge of a water course or water body. Along water courses, they may include strips with riparian vegetation with a width of up to 10 meters. There shall be no agricultural production on buffer strips.</p> <p>* Flower strips: strips where a mixture of flowering plants has been sown to provide forage for pollinators (whilst field margins and buffer strips are usually only grass).</p>				

Agroforestry and integrated farming

Q 39	<p>[A] In 2018 did you use any of the following agroforestry practices? Only answer options that are relevant to farm. Please skip if not relevant</p>	<p>[B] When did you start using this system of practice?</p>	<p>[C] Across what % of your UAA did you apply this practice in 2018?</p>	<p>[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the UAA to which the practice is applied)</p>	
	<p>If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4</p>	<p>1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago</p>	<p>1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%</p>	<p>1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase</p>	
Q39_1	<p>Agroforestry on arable land [silvoarable, hedgerow, windbreak and riparian buffer strips *]</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>
Q39_2	<p>Agroforestry on permanent grassland [silvopastoral practices such as dehesa, montado, wood pasture; and hedgerows, windbreaks, and riparian buffer strips *]</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>
Q39_3	<p>Agroforestry with perennial crops [grazing and intercropping * of perennial crops]</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5</p>
Notes	<p>* Buffer strips: herbaceous cover adjacent to cropland minimum width 1 meter (but single member states can increase it). They shall be located on or adjacent to a field in such a way that their long edges are parallel to the edge of a water course or water body. Along water courses, they may include strips with riparian vegetation with a width of up to 10 meters. There shall be no agricultural production on buffer strips.</p> <p>* Intercropping: growing two or more crops as a mixture in the same field at the same time. Intercropping can be one way of adding diversity to a crop system. It is a form of mixed cropping **.</p> <p>** Mixed cropping: a system of sowing two or three crops together on the same land, one being the main crop and the others the subsidiaries.</p>				

Water management

Q 40	[A] In 2018 did you irrigate your land? Only answer options that are relevant to farm. Please skip if not relevant	[B] When did you start irrigating?	[C] What was the extent of irrigation on your farm in 2018?		[D] From where did you source your water in 2018? (Multiple answers allowed)	[E] In the next five years do you plan to change irrigation on your land? (changes relate to the area that is irrigated or to the water quantity)
	If No ► go to column [E] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	Water consumption from irrigation in 2018 in litres	Percentage of UAA that is irrigated in 2018 (%)	1-Rainfall storage 2-Natural surface water courses 3-Artificial surface water courses 4-Ground water 5-Mains water supply 6-Other	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q40_1	Irrigation (arable and perennial crop area) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q40_2	Irrigation (pasture area) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Q 41	[A] In 2018 did you use precision technologies to determine the application rate or frequency of irrigation?	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] Across what % of your irrigated area (NOT the % of your UAA) did you apply this practice in 2018?	[D] In the next five years do you plan to change the practice that you use? (changes relate to the area to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [D] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1- ≤5% 2- >5% ≤ 25% 3- >25% ≤ 50% 4- >50% ≤ 75% 5- >75% ≤ 100%	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q41_1	Soil mapping <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q41_2	Soil moisture sensing <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q41_3	Variable rate irrigation <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Mechanisation

Q 42	Please provide the following information for your machinery:	[A] Value and quantity in year 2018	[B] Specify currency	[C] In the next five years do you intend to change the value or quantity?
				1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q42_1	Depreciation value of the machinery owned (aggregated value for the whole farm)			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q42_2	Amount paid for machinery rented * in (aggregated value for the whole farm)			<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q42_3a	Quantity of total fuel consumed for machinery	_____ Litres		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q42_3b	AND (OR, if impossible to answer both) Cost of total fuel consumed for machinery	_____ Currency		
Notes	* Cost for machinery rented is only for the machinery and does not include the drivers' fee.			

Energy management

Q 43	[A] In 2018 did you use a listed energy management practice on your farm? (family house is excluded)	[B] When did you start using this practice?	[C] In the next five years do you plan to change this practice? (changes relate to the size of equipment to which the practice is applied)
	If No ► go to column [C] where you should select between options 3 and 4	1- Less than 5 years ago 2- 5-10 years ago 3- More than 10 years ago	1-Reduce 2-Stop 3-No change 4-Start 5-Increase
Q43_1	Specific buildings (e.g. thermal insulation, passive energy building) <u>with</u> recognised energetic certification	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3
Q43_2	Specific buildings (e.g. thermal insulation, passive energy building) <u>without</u> recognised energetic certification	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_3	Photovoltaic panels (electricity production)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_4	Solar panels (heat production)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_5	Wind turbines	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_6 Q43_6a	Biomass combustion If yes, specify if biomass from (multiple selections allowed): <input type="checkbox"/> own farm, <input type="checkbox"/> neighbouring farm, <input type="checkbox"/> other farm	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_7	Geothermal	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
Q43_8	Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Section 3

Drivers of practices' adoption

This section will ask you about factors that influence the farming practices that you use.

It may sometimes refer to **ecological farming practices**. As described in the introduction this term refers to farming practices understood to have environmental and / or social benefits.

Environmental benefits might include, but are not limited to: improved soil or water quality, conserving biodiversity, or reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Social benefits may include, but are not limited to: animal health and welfare, promoting social capital in rural communities, or maintaining the rural landscape and heritage.

Q 44 Do you discuss your farming practices with the buyers of your products?						
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q44_1	I discuss the environmental and social benefits of my farming practices with those who buy my products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q44_2	My farming practices are regularly assessed against environmental and/or social farming practice standards by those who buy my products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q44_3	The requirements of those who buy my products restrict my ability to farm using more ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q44_4	The buyers of my products have little interest in the farming practices that I use	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q44_5	The buyers of my products and me share information about product quality but not farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	<i>Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.</i>					

Q 45		How would you describe your relationship with the buyers of your products?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q45_1	Our relationship is truthful and frank	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q45_2	Our relationship is fair and equal	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q45_3	We have a long-term relationship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q45_4	We have a partnership	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q45_5	I always deal with the same individuals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Informal institutional conditions and social norms

Q 46_A		How often do you consult the following sources of information to get ideas for farming practices?					
		At least monthly	Several times per year	Once a year	Less than once a year	Never	
Q46_1	Family and friends	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_2	Business partners (in the farm)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_3	Agricultural advisors*	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_4	Environmental advisors *	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_5	Supplier representatives *	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_6	Buyer representatives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_7	Open days, demonstration activities, training	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_8	Other farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_9	Press/Radio/TV	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q46_10	Internet (including social media)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q 46_B		Same question for organisations of which you are a member					
	<i>Tick last column if you are not a member</i>	At least monthly	Several times per year	Once a year	Less than once a year	Never	I am not a member
Q46_11	Conservation and farming NGO	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_12	Farmer/grower organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_13	Farmers union	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_14	Landowners association	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_15	Cooperative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_16	Certification body	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q46_17	Other (please specify / _____/)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Advisors include extension agents, private consultants, associations. * Supplier representatives may include sales representatives or consultants provided by those from whom you purchase feed, seed, pesticides etc., including veterinary service providers.						

Q 47		How do you think other people view the use ecological practices *?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q47_1	The sources of information I consult regularly (see previous question) promote the use of ecological practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q47_2	People whose opinions I value are supportive of using ecological practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q47_3	There is societal expectation for farmers to use practices that generate environmental and / or social benefits beyond food production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Q 48		How do other farmers you know view the adoption of ecological farming practices *?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q48_1	There is a lot of agreement amongst farmers I know that using ecological farming practices is a good thing to do	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q48_2	Most farmers I know question using more ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q48_3	Few farmers I know are using ecological practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q48_4	Most farmers I know have not considered applying ecological farming practices beyond what is required by regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q48_5	Most farmers that I know have adopted at least one practice that could be considered ecological	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Q 49		To what extent do you agree with the following statement about farmers and farming?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q49_1	Being a farmer is an important reflection of who I am	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q49_2	What happens to farmers as a whole will have an effect on what happens in my life	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q49_3	I have a strong sense of belonging to the farming community	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q49_4	I see myself as a farmer who prioritises the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q49_5	Understanding the ecology of the farm is what farming is about	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q49_6	Farming in a way that preserves the environment is part of who I am	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 50		Which of the following are important when you make decisions about the farming practices you use?				
		Not at all important 1	Unimportant 2	Neither important nor unimportant 3	Important 4	Very important 5
Q50_1	Seeing the practice implemented on another farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q50_2	Knowing the practice is widespread on farms like mine	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q50_3	Knowing the practice is innovative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Individual motivational factors

Q 51		How important are the following objectives to you?				
		Not at all important 1	Unimportant 2	Neither important nor unimportant 3	Important 4	Very Important 5
Q51_1	Maximising profits	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_2	Producing high quality products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_3	Maximising production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_4	Expanding the business	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_5	Being innovative e.g. using new technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_6	Meeting challenges	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_7	Minimising financial risk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_8	Being fit and healthy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_9	Providing a satisfying lifestyle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_10	Farming in a way that enhances the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_11	Improving the condition of the land	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q51_12	Protecting the environment for future generations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 52		To what extent do you agree with the following statements?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q52_1	Taking steps to protect the environment only makes sense to the extent that they benefit agricultural production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q52_2	Natural areas are important to maintain or create only if they provide productivity benefits for my farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q52_3	Protecting the environment is an important part of my job	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q52_4	It is important to adopt farming practices that provide environmental or social benefits	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q52_5	It is important to continuously assess the environmental and social impact of my farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 53		To what extent do the following statements describe your management style?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q53_1	I like to mull over a decision before acting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_2	Keeping records and calculating outcomes before making a decision is important	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_3	I do not like to take risky decisions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_4	I tend to postpone investment decisions until they really need to be done	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_5	I tolerate mistakes when making changes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_6	Trialling new practices is exciting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_7	Making changes to well-established practices is a real pain	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q53_8	I try to take a preventative rather than a remedial approach	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 54		In the last 5 years (or since you began farming if sooner than 5 years) have you observed, in your area, an increase or a decrease in the following:				
		Large decrease 1	Slight decrease 2	Have not noticed a change 3	Slight increase 4	Large increase 5
Q54_1	Number of extreme weather events	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_2	Number of beneficial insects e.g. pollinators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_3	Number of species of birds	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_4	Number of species of mammals (excluding invasive species)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_5	Soil erosion	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_6	Number of flooding events	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_7	Soil quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q54_8	Other changes observed to land and the environment (please specify / _____/)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 55		How easy or difficult is it to achieve the following objectives on your farm?				
If you feel you have already met this objective please answer in relation to how easy or difficult it WAS to achieve. Otherwise, please reflect on how easy or difficult the objective is likely to achieve.						
		Very difficult 1	Difficult 2	Neither difficult nor easy 3	Easy 4	Very easy 5
Q55_1	Improve the soil condition on your farm (i.e. organic matter content and biological activity)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_2	Find effective alternatives to synthetic products (fertilisers, pesticides, herbicides)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_3	Recycle more biomass from your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_4	Minimise resource losses from soil or water on your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_5	Maintain or create wildlife habitats on your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_6	Integrate different agro-ecosystems on your farm (i.e. crop and livestock systems, or different cropping systems)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_7	Increase genetic diversity (crops or livestock) on your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q55_8	Farm in a more extensive manner	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 56		How prepared do you feel to use more ecological farming practices * in the next 5 years?				
		Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
Q56_1	I feel well prepared to use more ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_2	I always meet the goals I set for myself (the farm)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_3	I have access to good advice and support on ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_4	There are not many opportunities open to me in the market that would enable me to adopt more ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_5	I do not have the knowledge and skills to adopt more ecological farming practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_6	Ecological farming practices are easy to use	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q56_7	Ecological farming practices are easy to understand	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Benefits, triggers and barriers

Q 57		What effect has adoption of ecological farming practices * had on the following outcomes?				
If you do not currently use ecological farming practices, please consider the effect you believe their adoption WOULD have.		Large decrease 1	Slight decrease 2	No change 3	Slight increase 4	Large increase 5
Q57_1	Profitability of your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_2	Production of your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_3	Labour requirements for your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_4	Your ability to meet current and future farm support payment requirements	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_5	Your ability to meet your farming objectives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_6	Your time spent working on the farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_7	Soil quality on your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_8	Your farm's dependence on external inputs *	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_9	Biodiversity on your farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_10	Intensity of seasonal peaks of work during the year (for you and the other farm workers)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_11	Physical nature of work (for you and the other farm workers)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q57_12	Mental workload (for you and the other farm workers)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits. * External inputs include anything brought onto the farm such as fertiliser or feed.					

Q 58 Thinking about the last time you changed the farming practices you use, how important were the following factors? If you have never made any changes to your farming practices, please consider how important the following factors WOULD be if you were to make a change.						
		Not at all important 1	Unimportant 2	Neither important nor unimportant 3	Important 4	Very important 5
Q58_1	Ability to cope with pests and diseases	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_2	Ability to cope with changing weather	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_3	Ability to observe and measure benefits of the practice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_4	Fit with the way you currently farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_5	Cost of adoption	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_6	Market reward	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_7	Supply chain contract restrictions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_8	Ability to meet product quality or safety standards	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_9	Amount of skilled labour required (hired labour or training)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_10	Personal challenge and interest	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q58_11	Availability of advice and support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 59 Thinking about the last time you have made a decision to change the farming practices you use, which of the following events were important? If you have never made any changes to your farming practices, please consider whether these events WOULD likely be an important influence on future changes.						
		Not at all important 1	Unimportant 2	Neither important nor unimportant 3	Important 4	Very important 5
Q59_1	Changes in input prices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_2	Changes in product prices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_3	Financial difficulties	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_4	Availability of skilled labour	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_5	Land availability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_6	Changes in weather patterns	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_7	Changes to regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_8	Availability of new technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_9	Planning for succession	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_10	Inheriting farm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q59_11	New market opportunities (domestic or export)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q 60 Thinking about the last time you have adopted one or some ecological farming practices *, how have the farm's labour requirements changed? If you have never adopted ecological farming practices, please consider whether these WOULD likely change.		Large decrease 1	Slight decrease 2	No change 3	Slight increase 4	Large increase 5
Q60_1	Farm managers' labour	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_2	Family full time labour (exclude farm managers if they fall in this category)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_3	Family part time labour (exclude farm managers if they fall in this category)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_4	Hired full time labour	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_4a	Thereof: hired full time labour from workers from another country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_5	Hired part time labour	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q60_5a	Thereof: hired part time labour from workers from another country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Q 61 Thinking about the last time you have adopted one or some ecological farming practices *, how have the skill requirements for farm work and management changed? If you have never adopted ecological farming practices, please consider whether these WOULD likely change.		Large decrease 1	Slight decrease 2	No change 3	Slight increase 4	Large increase 5
Q61_1	Skill requirements for farm work and management: change for farm manager(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q61_2	Skill requirements for farm work and management: change for other farm workers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Section 4

Farm structural and economic information

All questions relate to the year 2018 or to the timespan 2016-2018 (the indication is given in each question), unless otherwise indicated.

A year may be the calendar year (January to December), the seasonal year or the tax year: it is up to you to decide which year is best suited for your case, but one year should be 12 months long.

Factors of production – Land

Q 62 In case you know it, how much was the average price for rented agricultural land in your area in 2018?			
		Average price for 1 Ha rented land in your area in 2018 (in national currency per hectare)	Specify currency
Q62_1	Arable land	/ Ha	
Q62_2	Pastures/Meadows	/ Ha	
Q62_3	Orchards excluding olives (if relevant in the region)	_____/ Ha <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant in the area	
Q62_4	Olives (if relevant in the region)	_____/ Ha <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant in the area	
Q62_5	Vineyards (if relevant in the region)	_____/ Ha <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant in the area	
Q62_6	Forest (if relevant in the region)	_____/ Ha <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant in the area	

Factors of production – Farm buildings

Q 63		Please describe farm buildings for agricultural purposes FULLY or PARTIALLY owned (not rented) (at the end of 2018. Please consider only such sheds with a firm building foundation! (e.g. made out of concrete, wood... No tents, no huts...))			As we assume the average use of a building is 30 years, please describe the investment costs for construction and major re-constructions of the buildings. For sheds, please describe costs only for the building, we'll ask for equipment (milking technique, installations) in the next question		
		[A] Total size	[B] Specify unit for size	[C] % of size of owned buildings in full ownership	[D] Total investment costs in this building-type since 1988 (Construction and reconstruction cost, at the time of the investment)	[E] Specify currency	[F] Majority of investment costs since 1988 occurred...
Sheds							
Q63_1a	Cow shed(s); Specify type (e.g. playpen, tethering, ...): / _____ /		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1b	Sheep shed(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1c	Goat shed(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1d	Pig shed(s); Specify type and system (e.g. outdoor climate houses, slatted floor, ...): / _____ /		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1e	Chicken shed(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1f	Turkey shed(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago

							<input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1g	Other poultry shed(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_1h	Other sheds; Specify: / _____ /		<input type="checkbox"/> places <input type="checkbox"/> m2				<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Storage and machinery buildings							
Q63_2a	Buildings for crop storage			m2			<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_2b	Silo(s)			m3			<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_2c	Machinery building(s)			m2			<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_2d	Greenhouses			m2			<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years
Q63_2e	Other farm buildings (e.g. feed storage) Specify: / _____ /			m2			<input type="checkbox"/> in the last 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> more than 20 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> equally distributed over the last 30 years

Factors of production – Machinery

Q 64								
What kind of agricultural equipment FULLY OWNED and PARTIALLY OWNED (SHARED) do you normally/typically use (average over years 2016 – 2018)?								
		Fully owned machinery use		Partially owned (i.e. shared*) machinery use		For leading machinery (self-propelled machinery such as tractors/harvesters but also big investments such as hay drying machinery, milking system or robots), please specify year of acquisition and costs of acquisition		
Types of agricultural equipment		[A] Do you use own machinery?	[B] If yes, number of machinery owned	[C] Do you use shared* machinery?	[D] If yes, number of machinery shared*	[E] Year of acquisition	[F] Costs of acquisition	[G] Specify currency
Tractor and other towing vehicles								
Q64_1ai	Tractor	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Tractor 1		
Q64_1aii						Tractor 2:		
Q64_1aiiii						Tractor 3:		
Q64_1aiv						Tractor 4:		
Q64_1av						Tractor 5:		
Q64_1ai0 Q64_1ai1						Power of strongest tractor: _____ Specify unit: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> KW or <input type="checkbox"/> HP		
Q64_1b	Lorry, truck	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
Q64_1c	ATV, Quad bike	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
Q64_1d	Other tractor and other towing vehicles (please specify /_____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
Soil tillage machinery								
Q64_2a	Plough	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
Q64_2b	Cultivator	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				

Q64_2c	Other soil tillage machinery (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Planting machinery						
Q64_3a	Conventional seed drill	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_3b	Precision seed drill	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_3c	Direct seed drill	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_3d	Mulch seed drill	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_3e	Machinery for planting trees, vineyards	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_3f	Other planting machinery (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Fertilising and pest control machinery						
Q64_4a	Chemical spraying equipment (pesticides)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_4b	Chemical fertiliser spreader	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_4c	Liquid manure/slurry spreader equipment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_4d	Dry manure spreader	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_4e	Other fertilising and pest control machinery (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Irrigation equipment						
Q64_5a	Drip irrigation system	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_5b	Sprinkler system	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Q64_5c	Other irrigation equipment (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Harvesting machinery (crops and fruits)						
Q64_6ai	Self-propelled harvester (grain and corn)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Harvester 1
Q64_6aia						
Q64_6aib						
Q64_6aia						Harvester 2
Q64_6aib						
Q64_6bi	Self-propelled vegetable harvester	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Harvester 1
Q64_6bia						
Q64_6bib						
Q64_6bii						Harvester 2

Q64_6ci	Harvesting machine for fruits, olives, grapes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			Harvester 1		
Q64_6cii						Harvester 2		
Q64_6di	Self-propelled shredding machine (corn)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			Shredder 1		
Q64_6dii						Shredder 2		
Q64_6e	Baler (silage corn)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_6f	Other harvesting machinery for crops or fruits (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Harvesting machinery (grassland)								
Q64_7a	Disc mower	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7b	Bar mower	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7c	Baler (hay)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7d	Baler (silage grass)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7e	Hay drying: dehumidifier	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7f	Hay drying: hot air dryer	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7g	Hay drying: cold air dryer	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_7h	Other harvesting machinery for grassland (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Animal husbandry equipment								
Q64_8a	Milking system (e.g. fishbone parlour, tandem parlour, bucket milker, piped milking machine): Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_8b	Stable system, such as ventilation system, manure handling system, stabling (resting pens, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_8c	Other specific machinery for pig/poultry husbandry: Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Q64_8d	Other animal husbandry equipment: Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					

Robots							
Q64_9a	Milking robot	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Q64_9b	Driverless tractor	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Q64_9c	Fieldwork robot (e.g. harvesting, weed control)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Other machinery							
Q64_10a	Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Q64_10b	Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Notes	<i>* SHARED equipment is jointly owned with other farmers. We will separately ask for outsourced production processes in the next question.</i>						

Q 65						
Please indicate for the following production processes whether they are usually done on your farm, and whether you usually give some away via contract work (outsourcing e.g. hiring from machinery ring) (“usually” means that you should think of how you did these works in the years 2016 – 2018)						
	Production process	[A] In 2016-2018 were the following production processes done on your farm?	[B] If yes to [A], did you give them away (partly or fully) via contract work? <i>(machinery and added driver against payment e.g. machinery ring)</i>	If yes to [B]		
				[C] Please indicate the proportion of work you gave away via contract work (e.g. 33% if 1/3 of work is done through contract work)	[D] Indicate the usual costs for the contract work per year (including machinery and driver fee) *	[E] <i>Please specify the currency</i>
Soil tillage						
Q65_EX	EXAMPLE: Work is done 2/3 by farmer, 1/3 through contract work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	33 %	5,000	€
Q65_1a	Ploughing	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_1b	Soil tillage with cultivator	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_1c	Other soil tillage work (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Planting						
Q65_2a	Conventional seed drilling	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_2b	Precision seeding	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_2c	Direct seed drilling	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_2d	Mulch seed drilling *	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_2e	Planting of orchards, vineyards, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_2f	Other planting work (please specify / _____ /)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Fertilising and pest control						
Q65_3a	Chemical spraying (pesticides)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_3b	Chemical fertilising	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		

Q65_3c	Liquid manure/slurry spreading	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_3d	Dry manure spreading	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_3e	Other fertilising/pest control work (please specify / _____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Harvesting (crops and fruits)						
Q65_4a	Grain and corn harvesting (e.g. with a self-propelled harvester)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_4b	Vegetable harvesting (e.g. with a self-propelled harvester)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_4c	Harvesting fruits, olives, grapes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_4d	Silage maize harvesting (e.g. with a self-propelled shredding machine)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_4e	Baling (silage maize)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_4f	Other harvesting work for crops and fruits (please specify / _____/)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Harvesting (grassland)						
Q65_5a	Disc mowing	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_5b	Bar mowing	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_5c	Baling (hay)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_5d	Baling (silage grass)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_5e	Loading/transporting grass/hay	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Other works						
Q65_6a	Specify: /_____/	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_6b	Specify: /_____/	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_6c	Specify: /_____/	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Q65_6d	Specify: /_____/	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	%		
Notes	<p><i>Paying modalities for contract work may differ across countries. E.g. in some countries costs are paid by hours, in others by quantity of harvesting yield. Here to specify the best fitting option for the case study area (and to sum up to costs per year).</i></p> <p><i>* Mulch sowing is a ploughless sowing method in which the plant remains of a catch crop or the straw from the previous crop cover the soil surface before and after sowing, thus protecting it from soil erosion and silting up.</i></p>					

Fixed assets and investments

Q 66 In case you know the figures, please indicate for the years 2016 – 2018, for your farm’s owned assets (including those IN FULL AND IN SHARED ownership), the...				
		[A] Value	[B] Specify the currency	[C] Tick if you don’t know the value
Q66_1	... average asset value of your farm’s own assets			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
	Thereof (in case you know):			
Q66_1a	→ (a) average asset value of your farm’s owned agricultural buildings only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_1b	→ (b) average asset value of your farm’s owned agricultural machinery only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_1c	→ (c) average asset value of your farm’s owned orchards, olive groves and vineyards only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_2	... average total liabilities of your farm			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
	Thereof (in case you know):			
Q66_2a	→ (a) average total liabilities of agricultural buildings only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_2b	→ (b) average total liabilities of agricultural machinery only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_3	... average depreciation (i.e. indicate what is the annual depreciation)			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
	Thereof (in case you know):			
Q66_3a	→ (a) average depreciation of agricultural buildings only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_3b	→ (b) average depreciation of agricultural machinery only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_3c	→ (c) average depreciation of orchards, olive groves and vineyards only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_4	... average replacement investments (yearly costs for replacing/repairing existing buildings, machinery, equipment)			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
	Thereof (in case you know):			
Q66_4a	→ (a) average replacement investments for agricultural buildings only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_4b	→ (b) average replacement investments for agricultural machinery only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_5	... total value of major new investments * (investments in additional agricultural buildings, agricultural machinery, equipment over the years 2016-2018)			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
	Thereof (in case you know):			
Q66_5a	→ (a) total value of major new investments for agricultural buildings only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Q66_5b	→ (b) total value of major new investments for agricultural machinery only			<input type="checkbox"/> Don’t know
Notes	* A new investment means an investment which enlarges the number of machinery/equipment/buildings or the size of equipment/buildings. It is different than a replacement investment, which represents the costs for replacing machinery or for repair machinery each year.			

Q 67 In the case of new investments, or big replacement investments, what was the share of equity* used in 2016-2018?	
	_____ % of equity capital
Note	* Equity means capital raised from own resources to finance an investment. Not loan capital.

Variable inputs

Q 68 Please describe the regular inputs needed for your agricultural production (Average per year over the years 2016, 2017, 2018)								
	[A] TOTAL USED = PURCHASE + OWN PRODUCTION FOR OWN USE	PURCHASE: External inputs purchased for own use					OWN PRODUCTION for own use (not for sale)	
		Average quantity of purchased inputs per year		Average purchase price			Average quantity of inputs produced on your own farm per year	
		[B] Quantity	[C] Unit	[D] Price	[E] For which quantity (per unit or for total quantity per year)	[F] Currency	[G] Quantity	[H] Unit
Inputs for crop production								
Seeds, seedlings, plantlets, and other plant materials (conventional), please specify for your 10 most important crops, as regards contribution to farm income (please also think of forage for animals)								
Q68_1a	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1b	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1c	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1d	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1e	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1f	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1g	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity			<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> number

Q68_1h	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1i	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_1j	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Seeds, seedlings, plantlets, and other plant materials (organic), please specify for your 10 most important crops, as regards contribution to farm income (please also think of forage for animals)				
Q68_2a	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2b	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2c	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2d	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2e	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2f	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2g	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2h	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2i	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number
Q68_2j	Specify crop: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> number

Fertilisers, pest management, etc.							
Q68_3a	Animal manure (liquid)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_3b	Animal manure (solid)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_3c	Chemical fertiliser		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		
Q68_3d	Compost		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_3e	Chemical pesticides		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		
Q68_3f	Pesticides allowed in organic production		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_3g	Biological control (e.g. traps, predators, etc.); If used, specify: / _____ /				For total quantity		
Q68_3h	Other soil conditioners (microbial inoculant, mineral supplements)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_3i	Irrigation water				<input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		
Inputs for animal husbandry							
Feed for ruminants (cattle, sheep, goats)							
Q68_4a	Hay (conventional)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4b	Silage (conventional)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4c	Other forage (conventional)		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3		<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity		<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3

Q68_4d	Hay (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4e	Silage (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4f	Other forage (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4g	Feed grain (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4h	Feed grain (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4i	Concentrated feed (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4j	Concentrated feed (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4k	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4l	Protein feed (e.g. soy, peas, beans) (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_4m	Protein feed (e.g. soy, peas, beans) (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Feed for pigs				
Q68_5a	Feed grain (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5b	Feed grain (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5c	Concentrated feed (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3

Q68_5d	Concentrated feed (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5e	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5f	Soy (conventional) (e.g. soy oilcake, extracted meal, etc.) Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5g	Soy (organic) (e.g. soy oilcake, extracted meal, etc.) Specify: / _____ /	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5h	Potato protein (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5i	Potato protein (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5j	Feed peas (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_5k	Feed peas (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Feed for poultry				
Q68_6a	Feed grain (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6b	Feed grain (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6c	Concentrated feed (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6d	Concentrated feed (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6e	Mineral feed	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3

Q68_6f	Protein feed (e.g. soy, peas, beans) (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6g	Protein feed (e.g. soy, peas, beans) (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3
Q68_6h	Oil (conventional)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Q68_6i	Oil (organic)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre	<input type="checkbox"/> Per unit specified left <input type="checkbox"/> For total quantity	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre
Energy				
Q68_7a	Electricity	Kilowatt hours (KWh)	For total quantity	Kilowatt hours (KWh)
Q68_7b	Fuel for agricultural production	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre	For total quantity	
Q68_7c	Fuel for other processes (e.g. hay drying, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton <input type="checkbox"/> m3 <input type="checkbox"/> litre	For total quantity	
Other costs				
Q68_8a	Veterinary drugs and services		For total quantity	
Q68_8b	Insurances (crops, livestock, buildings, equipment)		For total quantity	
Q68_8c	Certification costs (for labels, organic farming, etc.)		For total quantity	
Q68_8d	Other costs (please specify): _____		For total quantity	

Outputs – Crops and horticulture

Q 69 Crop and horticulture production. If not relevant, please skip. Averages per year over 2016-2017-2018								
	Product	[A] Average cultivated area		[B] UNIT = Specify the quantity unit for yield and quantity sold	[C] Average yield (in UNIT per Ha per year)	[D] Average quantity sold (in UNIT per year)	[E] Average sale price (in currency per UNIT)	[F] Specify the currency
Q69_1	Wheat		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_2	Maize for grain		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_3	Maize for silage		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_4	Barley		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_5	Other cereals		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_6	Oilseeds (sunflower, rapeseed, etc.)		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_7	Fodder excluding silage maize (beet, pea, etc.)		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_8	Sugar beets		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_9	Potatoes		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_10	Pulses (beans, lentils etc.)		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_11	Greenhouse vegetables		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_12	Field vegetables		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_13	Grapes		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_14	Apples and other orchard fruits		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_15	Olives		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_16	Other fruits and berries		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_17	Hops		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_18	Tobacco		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_19	Hemp		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_20	Herbs and flowers		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_21	Nurseries		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				
Q69_22	Other		Ha	<input type="checkbox"/> kg <input type="checkbox"/> ton				

Outputs – Livestock

Q 70 Livestock purchases and sales. If not relevant, please skip. Yearly averages over 2016-2017-2018								
	Type of livestock	PURCHASES			SALES			[G] Specify the currency for both prices
		[A] Average number of animals purchased per year	[B] Average weight of purchased animal (in Kg per head)	[C] Average purchase price per animal (in currency per head)	[D] Average number of animals sold per year	[E] Average weight of sold alive animal (in Kg per head)	[F] Average sale price per animal (in currency per head)	
Q70_1	Dairy cows							
Q70_2	Cull dairy cows							
Q70_3	Calves for fattening							
Q70_4	Suckler cows							
Q70_5	Other cattle							
Q70_6	Goats (breeding females)							
Q70_7	Other goats							
Q70_8	Ewes							
Q70_9	Other sheep							
Q70_10	Breeding sows							
Q70_11	Other pigs							
Q70_12	Laying hens							
Q70_13	Other chicken							
Q70_14	Other poultry							
Q70_15	Other animals							

Outputs – Agricultural products

Q 71 Agricultural products. If not relevant, please skip. Yearly averages over 2016-2017-2018.								
	Product	[A] Average quantity produced per year		[B] Average quantity sold per year		Average sale price per year		
		Quantity		Quantity		[C] Price	[D] Unit	[E] Specify currency
Q71_1	Cow milk		Litres		Litres		/ Litre	
Q71_2	Sheep milk		Litres		Litres		/ Litre	
Q71_3	Goat milk		Litres		Litres		/ Litre	
Q71_4	Cheese		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_5	Butter		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_6	Yoghurt		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_7	Cream		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_8	Eggs		Pieces		Pieces		/ Piece	
Q71_9	Meat, raw or transformed except sausages		Kg		kg		/ Kg	
Q71_10	Sausages		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_11	Pickled vegetables		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_12	Jam		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_13	Wine		Litres		Litres		/ Litre	
Q71_14	Spirits		Litres		Litres		/ Litre	
Q71_15	Flour		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_16	Olive oil		Litres		Litres		/Litre	
Q71_17	Honey		Kg		Kg		/ Kg	
Q71_18	Timber		m3		m3		/ m3	
Q71_19	Other (specify / _____ /)		Specify unit: _____		Specify unit: _____		Specify unit: _____	

Section 5

Subsidies and income

Q 72 How much public subsidies did you receive for your farm in 2018? In case payment modalities are frequent (e.g. quarterly), please sum up to annual payments.			
		Value	Specify the currency
Q72_tot	Total amount of public subsidies in 2018 (this includes subsidies (a), (b), (c) and (d) below)	_____	
If possible, please describe the details of the subsidies you received in 2018			
Q72_a	(a) Total amount of EU subsidies from CAP 1st Pillar → Thereof:	_____	
Q72_ai	(i) Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment	_____	
Q72_aii	(ii) Coupled subsidies	_____	
Q72_b	(b) Total amount of EU subsidies from CAP 2nd Pillar → Thereof:	_____	
Q72_bi	(i) Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments	_____	
Q72_bii	(ii) Subsidies for organic farming	_____	
Q72_biii	(iii) Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)	_____	
Q72_biv	(iv) Other rural development payments (e.g. for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards etc.)	_____	
Q72_c	(c) Total amount of EU Payments linked to Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive	_____	
Q72_d	(d) Total amount of non-EU public subsidies (State, local government)	_____	

Q 73		Could you please indicate your total net household income in 2018?																		
Q73_A	Value: _____ (specify currency: _____)																			
Q73_B	<p>If you can't tell us the figure, please indicate a range your income lies within. <i>Notes: bands and currency to be adapted before survey per case study area.</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Very low</th> <th>Low</th> <th>Medium</th> <th>High</th> <th>Very high</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>< xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>> xx,xxx</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	< xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	> xx,xxx	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high																
< xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	> xx,xxx																
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>																
Notes	<p>Total household income is a measure of the combined incomes of all people belonging to the household*. It includes every form of income, e.g. farm income, salaries and wages from off-farm employment, retirement income, investment gains, etc.</p> <p>Total NET household income is total household income, after taxes and mandatory contributions (e.g. social-security) have been deducted.</p> <p>* A household consists of one or more people who live in the same home and share meals.</p>																			

Q 74		Could you please indicate your net household income from farming in 2018?																		
Q74_A	Value: _____ (specify currency: _____)																			
Q74_B	<p>If you can't tell us the figure, please indicate a range your income lies within. <i>Notes: bands and currency to be adapted before survey per case study area.</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Very low</th> <th>Low</th> <th>Medium</th> <th>High</th> <th>Very high</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>< xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>xx,xxx – xx,xxx</td> <td>> xx,xxx</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	< xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	> xx,xxx	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high																
< xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	xx,xxx – xx,xxx	> xx,xxx																
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>																
Notes	<p>Total household income is a measure of the combined incomes of all people belonging to the household*. It includes every form of income, e.g. farm income, salaries and wages from off-farm employment, retirement income, investment gains, etc.</p> <p>Total NET household income is total household income, after taxes and mandatory contributions (e.g. social-security) have been deducted.</p> <p>Net household income from farming is agricultural income, without forestry, agri-tourism, contract work, off farm employment.</p> <p>* A household consists of one or more people who live in the same home and share meals.</p>																			

Section 6

Contracting for agricultural outputs

Q 75	Which one of the following option best represents your marketing behaviour for your agricultural output?
	<input type="checkbox"/> [A] You decide to sell your next year's production in advance by contract and for this you are assured of a guaranteed price
	<input type="checkbox"/> [B] You decide to wait and sell your production later knowing that the price at the time of sales may be either higher or lower than the contract price in alternative [A]
	<input type="checkbox"/> [C] You are indifferent between the two options [A] and [B]

Q 76	In 2018 did you have at least one contract for your output?
Q76_1	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q76_2	If yes, the selling contract that generated the largest turnover * to you, was (<i>one answer only</i>):
	<input type="checkbox"/> An individual contract concluded on a stand-alone basis (<i>where a farmer is contracting directly with the firm</i>)
	<input type="checkbox"/> A collective framework contract (<i>where e.g. a producers' group or agricultural cooperative is contracting with a downstream firm, and each farmer has an individual contract with the producers' group or agricultural cooperative</i>)
Notes	* Turnover represents farm's income from net sales plus payments/subsidies before costs/taxes.

For this contract, please answer the following questions.

If you did not have a contract for your output in 2018, please go directly to next section.

Q 77	With whom did you, as a farmer, had this contract? <i>Multiple selections are allowed</i>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Group of farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Agricultural cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Processing firm <input type="checkbox"/> Retailer <input type="checkbox"/> Other (<i>please specify: / _____ /</i>)

Q 78	Did this contract specify any quality requirements you were bound to?
Q78_1	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q78_2	If yes, what were they based on? (<i>multiple selections are allowed</i>): <input type="checkbox"/> Origin of the input procurement <input type="checkbox"/> Input quality specification <input type="checkbox"/> Specific production process or technology adoption <input type="checkbox"/> Labour conditions <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental specification
Q78_3	If it was based on environmental specification, what did it concern? (<i>multiple selections are allowed</i>): <input type="checkbox"/> Pesticides use <input type="checkbox"/> Antibiotics use <input type="checkbox"/> Energy use <input type="checkbox"/> Soil quality <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity <input type="checkbox"/> Other environmental requirements (<i>please specify: / _____ /</i>)

Q 79	Did this contract specify any quantity requirements you were bound to? (<i>multiple selections are allowed</i>)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Fixed quantity (<i>The contract specified the amount to be delivered under the contract. It may be the total quantity produced.</i>) <input type="checkbox"/> A minimum quantity (<i>The contract specified a minimal production volume to be delivered.</i>) <input type="checkbox"/> No quantity requirements

Q 80	Did this contract specify any price formula? Please select below what was true for this contract. (multiple selections are allowed)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Fixed price (Such contract specifies a pre-determined price for which the product is delivered. If the market price is higher than the fixed price, the farmer will not benefit from this higher market price.)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Minimum price (Such contract guarantees a minimum price. If the market prices at the moment of delivery are higher than the specified minimum price, the farmer will benefit from this higher price.)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Spot market price (In this case, the price a farmer receives depends on the market price at the moment of delivery.)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Pooling price (Pool contracts average the market value of a commodity over a specified period. The price received reflects the average price over months of market activities.)
	<input type="checkbox"/> No price formula

Q 81	Did this contract specify any duration?
Q81_1	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q81_2	If yes, what was the specification? (multiple selections are allowed) <input type="checkbox"/> One year or less <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple years
Q81_3	If multiple years, please specify the number of years: _____ years

Q 82	Was this contract tacitly renewed?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Q 83	Did you have to make some investment to subscribe the contract?
Q83_1	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q83_2	If yes, what types of investment? (multiple selections are allowed) <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Training <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify: / _____ /)

Q 84	What other requirements did this contract enforce you to do?
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other requirements (please specify: / _____ /)
	<input type="checkbox"/> No other requirements

Section 7

Future policies

Q 85	According to you, should CAP Pillar I direct payments be more tightly linked with mandatory requirements on the adoption of ecological practices *?
Q_85	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q85_a	<p>If yes, what type of environmental requirements do you think should be mandatory to receive Pillar I direct payments? (<i>multiple selections are allowed</i>)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Achieving a given level of crop rotation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Preserving permanent grassland</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Maintaining some land specifically devoted to biodiversity-friendly practices</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Compliance with a farm sustainability tool on nutrient management **</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Protecting wetland/peatland</p>
Notes	<p>* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.</p> <p>**As part of the new CAP proposals for 2021-2027, a new tool is being developed to help farmers manage the use of nutrients on their farm: the Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients (FaST), a nutrient management plan, which gives customised recommendations on crop fertilisation for the farm selected.</p>

Q 86	To what extent do these statements describe your attitude and beliefs?					
		Strongly disagree	Some what disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Some what agree	Strongly agree
		1	2	3	4	5
Q86_1	Collaborative efforts in the adoption of ecological practices between neighbouring farmers should be rewarded	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q86_2	I can think of ecological practices * for which adoption by a sufficient share of neighbouring farmers would lower my cost of adoption	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q86_3	I am keen to participate in an agri-environmental scheme in which the amount of subsidy I receive depends on both me and my neighbours' uptake of new practices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q86_4	The environmental impact of my uptake of an ecological practice * can be impeded by my neighbours' decisions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Notes	* Ecological farming practices are those understood to promote environmental and/or social benefits.					

Q 87	Have you ever engaged in service provision arrangements with an environmental focus funded by:	
Q87_1	Public funds (excluding AES; e.g. funded by municipality)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q87_1a	If yes, what environmental issue(s) did it relate to? <i>(multiple selections are allowed)</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Water quality <input type="checkbox"/> Soil erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity <input type="checkbox"/> Flood control <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify: / _____ /)	
Q87_2	Private funds	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Q87_2a	If yes, what environmental issue(s) did it relate to? <i>(multiple selections are allowed)</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Water quality <input type="checkbox"/> Soil erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity <input type="checkbox"/> Flood control <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify: / _____ /)	

Q 88	Have you ever benefited from <i>de minimis</i> aid *?	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know	
Q88_a	If yes, what environmental issue(s) did it relate to? <i>(multiple selections are allowed)</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Water quality <input type="checkbox"/> Soil erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity <input type="checkbox"/> Flood control <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify: / _____ /)	
Notes	* <i>The overall aim of the de minimis principle is allow comparatively small amounts of support to be offered without being caught by State aid rules. In the agricultural sector, de minimis aid is "aid granted to a single undertaking over a given period of time that does not exceed a certain fixed amount, is deemed not to meet all the criteria laid down in Article 107(1) of the Treaty and is therefore not subject to the notification procedure." (CE regulation 1408/2013, paragraph 2) (see https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/fr/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R1408). French exemples include: 'crédit d'impôt en faveur de l'agriculture biologique', 'exonération de la Taxe Foncière sur le Non Bâti au bénéfice de l'agriculture biologique'.</i>	

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME!